

FENUGREEK - A NEW PROMISING MEDICINAL PLANT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Relevance: In recent years, great attention has been paid to the development of medicinal plants in the country at the state level. In this regard, a number of resolutions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular, the Decree No. PF-139 dated May 20, 2022 "On measures to create an added value chain through the effective use of the raw material base of medicinal plants, support for processing", stipulates that all districts of the Republic should specialize in the cultivation of anise, saffron, lovage, lavender, stevia, chamomile, marigold, lovage, yarrow, yarrow, yarrow, peppermint and other medicinal plants, and in this regard, from 2022 to 2026, new medicinal plant plantations will be established on an area of 36,000 hectares. In 2017, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5032 "On the establishment of the free economic zones "Nukus-Farm", "Zomin-Farm", "Kosonsoy-Farm", "Syrdaryo-Farm", "Boysun-Farm", "Bostonliq-Farm", "Parkent-Farm" also provided for the establishment of the cultivation of medicinal plants in these territories. In order to ensure the implementation of this Decree Nova Pharm JV has acquired the Boysun-farm land plot for the cultivation of various medicinal plants, in particular turmeric and fenugreek plants imported from India, which are used as raw materials for Ayurvedic medicines.

The purpose of the study: Studying the fenugreek plant from literature.

Methods and techniques: It is known from the literature that Fenugreek seeds contain a rich composition of antioxidant compounds and elements that provide anti-inflammatory effects. In addition, it contains the alkaloid trigonelline, which prevents the degeneration of nerve cells. It contains phytoestrogens, which are involved in the correction of endocrine disorders in women. In addition, it contains nicotinic acid, essential and fatty oils, steroid saponins, flavonoids, phytosterols and phytosterols, tannins, vitamins A, C and B1, B2, B9, lecithin and many other elements (iron, phosphorus, sodium, copper, zinc, selenium, magnesium, potassium). Also, fenugreek seeds contain almost all the amino acids necessary for the human body, including lysine and L-tryptophan.

Results: In ancient treatises, fenugreek was called a cure for forty diseases, we will list some of its beneficial properties and the diseases it treats: it has a positive effect on the functioning of the nervous system, improves mood and emotional state, maintains memory and attention; improves the cardiovascular system; normalizes fat metabolism; provides prevention and protection against joint diseases; prevents the development of diabetes; improves immunity; increases the regenerative capacity of organs; saturates cells with oxygen and normalizes water balance; has an antioxidant effect and improves heart function; cleanses from toxins and slags, removes heavy metals, stabilizes cell activity; makes the appearance attractive and makes the skin, nails and hair healthy; fenugreek treats constipation, hemorrhoids and edema. It improves metabolism, has a hypoglycemic effect, that is, it is aimed at reducing blood glucose levels, stimulates insulin secretion, reduces insulin resistance (cells become resistant to insulin and do not respond to the hormone insulin, cannot use it effectively, as a result of which every cell in the body goes hungry, experiences a glucose deficiency), restores pancreatic cells.

Conclusions: Based on the above data, it was determined that it is possible to develop a biologically active supplement in capsule form from Fenugreek seeds to normalize blood sugar and cholesterol levels, increase immunity, and improve appearance.